

Drift Adaptation as Supervision Routing under Heterogeneous Costs

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Abstract. Concept drift is a major source of failure in industrial edge systems, where adaptation is limited under scarce and costly supervision. Existing methods frame drift handling as uncertainty-based sampling, overlooking latency, financial cost, and constrained human attention. We formulate drift adaptation as *supervision routing* under resource constraints. We realize this view in **Symbiosis-Edge**, a cost-theoretic framework that routes uncertain instances across three agents: a lightweight edge model, an LLM oracle, and a human expert. Each instance is assigned to the least costly agent that achieves sufficient expected utility under supervision budgets. Experiments on synthetic, industrial, and live LLM-driven streams show recovery within a median of 40 samples and up to twice the supervision efficiency of uncertainty-sampling baselines in our evaluated settings. These results establish supervision routing as the operative form of drift adaptation under heterogeneous supervision costs. Code available at: <https://github.com/jorge-martinez-gil/symbiosis-edge>

Keywords: Concept Drift · Edge AI · Industry 5.0 · Drift adaptation · Cost-minimizing Routing Policy

1 Introduction

Industrial monitoring systems operate continuously, yet expert supervision is scarce and costly. During concept drift events, edge models degrade rapidly, and large-scale human intervention is impractical. Local Edge AI offers fast inference but cannot reason about new operating regimes or adapt beyond incremental parameter updates. These systems play a central role in Industry 5.0, providing low-latency inference, local data processing for privacy, and reduced bandwidth usage. Current deployments still face serious limitations in dynamic industrial environments [7]. Most rely on static models, lack mechanisms to incorporate expert feedback, and provide limited explainability in safety-critical settings.

Industrial edge AI combines streaming data processing, model lifecycle management, and human-machine collaboration. Traditional database architectures based on centralized warehouses cannot meet the real-time requirements and distributed structure of edge environments. Integrating human feedback into continuous model recalibration also requires versioning, provenance tracking, and quality control mechanisms that current edge AI platforms rarely support [18]. In adaptive industrial AI, provenance must extend beyond raw sensor data to include predictions, explanations, and model update events, enabling full auditability and accountability. This view aligns with recent arguments that large language models will reshape data management [6], treating LLM interactions as structured data artifacts subject to traceable lineage and repeatable analysis.

SYMBIOSIS-EDGE models the edge system, an LLM oracle, and the human operator as three agents in a cost-utility optimization process (Figure 1). Rather than deciding which samples humans should label, as in active learning, the framework determines which supervision agent should resolve each uncertain instance under explicit resource constraints. The LLM also generates *explanatory hypotheses* for anomalies that humans validate. This shifts the human role from label generation to reasoning, reducing the effort required for model recalibration. Our main contributions are:

1. We formulate drift adaptation as supervision routing, where uncertainty resolution becomes a routing problem across agents with different costs and reliability.
2. We define a tripartite coordination mechanism across an edge model, an LLM oracle, and a human expert that routes queries by expected utility rather than escalating directly to humans.
3. We define a budget-controlled thresholding strategy based on entropy quantiles and evaluate it with Accuracy Gain per Unit Cost (AGUC), a metric that measures the efficiency of streaming supervision under drift.
4. We empirically show on three streaming fault-classification benchmarks that our method recovers faster after drift and yields better cost-accuracy trade-offs than SAL and ADWIN-SAL.

Scope and Primary Claims. Unlike classical active learning, which optimizes query timing under a single supervision source, we treat drift adaptation as supervision routing across heterogeneous agents with distinct cost-quality profiles. Under this setting, routing, not query selection, is the central decision, with active learning appearing only as the single-oracle limit. We formalize this view through a cost-theoretic model and show that routing supervision across agents yields higher cost-efficiency than single-source querying. Our evaluation isolates routing decisions in a controlled setting where LLM and human supervision act as channels with distinct cost and reliability, enabling validation independent of implementation-specific assumptions.

The remainder of the paper presents the formal model (Section 2), the system architecture (Section 3), adaptive entropy thresholding (Section 4), experimental evaluation (Section 5), related work (Section 6), and conclusions (Section 7).

Fig. 1: Processing flow in SYMBIOSIS-EDGE. Supervision is a scarce resource that must be routed through a cost hierarchy. Uncertainty determines whether the Edge, Oracle, or Human handles samples. Cost acts as the decision constraint.

2 A Cost-Theoretic Model for Symbiotic Drift Adaptation

Unlike classical active learning, which assumes a single supervision source, we model supervision as a set of heterogeneous agents with different costs and capabilities, and formulate drift adaptation as supervision routing across them.

We consider a classification task over a streaming dataset $S = \{(x_t, y_t)\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$. At each time step t , the system produces a prediction \hat{y}_t and determines whether its internal model should be updated. Within this setting, we focus on the problem of *Supervision Escalation Cascade*. During concept drift, model uncertainty increases and systems tend to escalate more queries to human experts. This behavior raises costs and latency, limiting the scalability of adaptive learning.

2.1 The Tripartite Agents

We define three distinct agents participating in the inference process:

1. **The Edge Agent (\mathcal{E}):** A lightweight model (e.g., TensorFlow Lite) residing on the device. It has cost $C_{\mathcal{E}} \approx 0$ but suffers from drift.
2. **The Oracle (\mathcal{O}):** A model capable of zero-shot reasoning (e.g., LLM). It has a moderate cost $C_{\mathcal{O}}$ (latency/financial) and broad reasoning capacity. Its role is model-agnostic; any intermediate-cost reasoning system can instantiate it.
3. **The Human Expert (\mathcal{H}):** The ground truth authority. High cost $C_{\mathcal{H}}$ (effort/time) and negligible error. It is an upper-bound supervision channel.

2.2 The Optimization Problem

When supervision sources have different costs and capabilities, the system routes queries across them rather than escalating directly to humans. Therefore, let $\pi(x_t) \in \{\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{H}\}$ be the routing policy for an input x_t . The objective is to minimize the total accumulated cost J over a sliding window W of length $|W|$:

$$J = \sum_{t \in W} (\mathbb{I}(\hat{y}_t \neq y_t) \cdot \lambda_{err} + C_{\pi(x_t)}) \quad (1)$$

Where λ_{err} is the penalty for misclassification. The challenge is that y_t is unknown unless $\pi(x_t) = \mathcal{H}$.

2.3 Stability Under Stationary Segments

Let $C_{\mathcal{E}}$, $C_{\mathcal{O}}$, and $C_{\mathcal{H}}$ denote the per-query costs. Let $u_{\mathcal{E}}(x)$ denote the uncertainty assigned by the edge model to sample x . We partition the input space into three regions: $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{E}}$ for samples handled directly at the edge, $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{O}}$ for samples escalated to the oracle, and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}}$ for samples escalated to the human.

Proposition 1 (Cost Convergence under Stationary Supervision). *Let S be a stationary segment with strictly ordered costs $C_{\mathcal{E}} < C_{\mathcal{O}} < C_{\mathcal{H}}$, and let $\pi_t: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{H}\}$ route each instance to the least costly agent whose expected utility exceeds a resolution threshold, subject to budget constraints $B_{\mathcal{O}}, B_{\mathcal{H}}$ enforced via adaptive quantile thresholds (Eqs. 8–9). If online updates satisfy $\mathbb{E}[u_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t+1)}(x) \mid x \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t)}] \leq \mathbb{E}[u_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t)}(x) \mid x \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t)}]$, then $\mathbb{E}[C_{\pi_t(x_t)}] \leq (1 - B_{\mathcal{O}} - B_{\mathcal{H}}) C_{\mathcal{E}} + B_{\mathcal{O}} C_{\mathcal{O}} + B_{\mathcal{H}} C_{\mathcal{H}}$ for all t , and the edge error over $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t)}$ is non-increasing in t .*

Proof. The quantile thresholds ensure $\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{O}}^{(t)}) \leq B_{\mathcal{O}}$ and $\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{H}}^{(t)}) \leq B_{\mathcal{H}}$ by construction, so $\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t)}) \geq 1 - B_{\mathcal{O}} - B_{\mathcal{H}}$. The cost bound follows by linearity of expectation over the partition with $C_{\mathcal{E}} \leq C_{\mathcal{O}} \leq C_{\mathcal{H}}$. The adaptive thresholds track the entropy distribution, keeping routing fractions at budget levels while shifting progressively easier instances to the edge; the conditional entropy reduction then yields non-increasing edge error over $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{E}}^{(t)}$.

This result shows that, under stationarity, escalation minimization follows from cost ordering rather than from heuristic design.

Our agents act as service providers, and this stability follows from monotone cost ordering together with uncertainty reduction. For each sample x , uncertainty is computed from a proxy predictive distribution

$$\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{E}}(x) = (p_1(x), \dots, p_K(x)), \quad (2)$$

where K is the number of classes and $\sum_{k=1}^K p_k(x) = 1$. The uncertainty score is the Shannon entropy

$$u_{\mathcal{E}}(x) = - \sum_{k=1}^K p_k(x) \log p_k(x). \quad (3)$$

This proxy softmax distribution is constructed in a single pass from the edge model’s output logits, without additional calibration or temperature scaling. This choice reflects the raw confidence signal available at the edge and avoids extra hyperparameters that could interfere with budget-controlled routing.

Entropy as a routing signal. The policy uses entropy primarily as an ordering signal that separates routine cases from ambiguous ones under edge constraints. The budget controller (Section 4) depends on quantiles of the entropy stream rather than on calibrated probabilities. Therefore, the method requires that higher entropy correlates with higher error risk on average, not that entropy is perfectly calibrated. This choice keeps routing computable in a single forward pass and prevents additional calibration parameters from interacting with budget control.

3 System Architecture and Implementation

We adopt a three-layer architecture that separates communication, inference, and reasoning concerns. This architecture is invariant to oracle implementation.

3.1 Architecture for Cost-Aware Edge-LLM Coordination

The system follows a three-layer architecture that separates communication, inference, and reasoning. The communication layer uses MQTT over WebSockets for low-latency transport and maps sensor data into feature vectors. The inference layer processes these vectors with quantized models (TensorFlow Lite), enabling efficient execution without specialized hardware. A bridge connects edge processes to cloud-based generative AI. Structured prompts produce machine-readable JSON outputs containing predictions and explanations.

3.2 Online Parameter Adaptation Strategy

To address concept drift without incurring the latency of full model retraining, we implement an *Edge-Local Online Transfer Learning* mechanism. This approach treats the adaptation process as a partial weight-update problem constrained to the neural network’s classification head.

Let the edge model f_θ be defined as a composition of a feature extractor ϕ with parameters θ_ϕ and a classifier head ψ with parameters θ_ψ , such that:

$$f_\theta(x) = \psi(\phi(x; \theta_\phi); \theta_\psi) \quad (4)$$

In standard edge deployment, θ is immutable. In our framework, we define a mutable parameter subset $\theta_{active} = \theta_\psi$, while the feature extraction parameters $\theta_{frozen} = \theta_\phi$ remain static to preserve the generalized feature space learned during offline training.

Upon receiving a validated tuple (x_t, y_{true}) from either the Oracle \mathcal{O} or the Human Expert \mathcal{H} , the system performs a gradient descent step. The objective is to reduce the local loss \mathcal{L} (e.g., Cross-Entropy) solely with respect to θ_ψ :

$$\theta_\psi^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \theta_\psi^{(t)} - \eta \cdot \nabla_{\theta_\psi} \mathcal{L}(f(x_t), y_{true}) \quad (5)$$

where η is the learning rate, by freezing θ_ϕ , we decrease the computational cost of the backward pass and mitigate the risk of catastrophic forgetting, guaranteeing that the model adjusts to the new operating condition (e.g., machine speed change) without destroying its ability to recognize previous stable states.

4 Budget-Aware Threshold Adaptation

Static entropy thresholds suffer from two failure modes: they either flood the human expert during drift events or starve the adaptation process during stable periods. To address this, we derive a *Distribution-Free Budget Adaptation* mechanism to recover from concept drift without overwhelming human experts, maintaining high accuracy while enforcing strict supervision budgets.

4.1 Formalizing Resource Constraints

We define $\mathcal{B}_\mathcal{H}$ and $\mathcal{B}_\mathcal{O}$ as the maximum allowable query rates (budget) for the Human Expert and Oracle, respectively, defined as fractions of the data stream volume (e.g., $\mathcal{B}_\mathcal{H} = 0.05$ implies max 5% human load).

Our objective is to find dynamic thresholds $\tau_1(t), \tau_2(t)$ such that the routing probabilities satisfy:

$$P(u_t > \tau_2) \leq \mathcal{B}_\mathcal{H} \quad (6)$$

$$P(\tau_1 < u_t \leq \tau_2) \leq \mathcal{B}_\mathcal{O} \quad (7)$$

4.2 Sliding Window Quantile Estimation

Let \mathcal{D}_W be the empirical distribution of entropy values u_t over a sliding window W . To strictly enforce the budget constraints, we invert the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of \mathcal{D}_W . The thresholds are dynamically updated as:

$$\tau_2(t) = \text{Quantile}_{1-\mathcal{B}_\mathcal{H}}(\mathcal{D}_W) \quad (8)$$

$$\tau_1(t) = \text{Quantile}_{1-(\mathcal{B}_\mathcal{H}+\mathcal{B}_\mathcal{O})}(\mathcal{D}_W) \quad (9)$$

This ensures that query rates remain within the defined budgets, regardless of drift severity.

5 Experimental Evaluation

SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves higher accuracy at less than half the supervision cost across all datasets. We examine how this advantage emerges under distribution shift and persists across synthetic and industrial streams.

5.1 Experimental Setup

We evaluate SYMBIOSIS-EDGE on three data sources related to industrial monitoring: (i) a synthetic multi-class sensor stream with controlled distribution shift, (ii) the SECOM semiconductor manufacturing dataset, and (iii) the APS failure dataset from heavy-duty vehicles. All tasks follow an online fault classification setting under streaming conditions. Each experiment processes sequential samples, and results are averaged over 20 runs with different random seeds. Statistical significance is assessed with paired t -tests at $\alpha = 0.05$ across runs.

A controlled drift is injected at $t = 500$ in all streams by scaling vibration-related features with $\delta = 1.5$, simulating mechanical loosening. SECOM and APS also contain natural distribution changes caused by process variability.

We compare four approaches: (i) **Static Edge**, a fixed model without post-deployment supervision; (ii) **Standard Active Learning (SAL)**, using uncertainty sampling with query fraction $b_{\text{SAL}} = 0.15$; (iii) **ADWIN SAL** [3] ADWIN-triggered uncertainty sampling with a base query fraction $b_{\text{base}} = 0.10$ and an alarm-phase fraction $b_{\text{alarm}} = 0.28$; and (iv) **Symbiosis-Edge**, our budget-aware routing strategy $b_{\text{oracle}} = 0.10$ and $b_{\text{human}} = 0.05$.

Parameter values reflect typical industrial constraints. The stream length provides stable pre-drift observations and a sufficient post-drift segment for adaptation analysis. The drift point separates stable and perturbed regimes, and $\delta = 1.5$ produces a noticeable but realistic shift magnitude. Budget fractions reflect the cost and availability of supervision sources: oracle access is moderately available, matching SAL query volume for fair comparison, whereas human supervision is scarce and expensive ($b_{\text{human}} = 0.05$). Learning rates scale with reliability, keeping edge updates conservative.

SAL is a fixed-fraction uncertainty sampling policy for streaming data, and ADWIN-SAL extends it with drift-triggered query adaptation. We focus on these baselines because they are canonical uncertainty-sampling policies for streaming adaptation, allowing a direct test of whether budgeted supervision routing outperforms query-centric methods under matched supervision constraints.

Unless noted otherwise, we use normalized supervision units with edge = 0, oracle = 1, and human = 10; the method depends on cost ordering rather than absolute pricing, and SAL queries are costed as human supervision. Section 5.5 provides a detailed analysis of the sensitivity to this ratio. Reported metrics include mean accuracy, cumulative query counts, and supervision cost, computed over the post-drift segment. Figures show mean rolling accuracy (window size 25) with 95% confidence intervals across runs. Edge, Oracle, and Human are modeled as time-varying correctness probabilities. The Oracle is treated as a stochastic supervision channel whose reliability decreases monotonically with edge uncertainty. This abstraction is fixed across experiments to isolate routing behavior from oracle-specific implementation details. Drift is applied only at the environment level and hidden from the methods. Routing uses an entropy-based uncertainty proxy, while supervision budgets rely on quantile thresholds to keep query rates bounded.

Oracle, Cost Model, and Updates. The Oracle is a low-cost supervisor with weaker corrective impact than humans, and is calibrated to approximate realistic accuracy–cost trade-offs observed in practical scenarios. The costs are justified in 5.5, and facilitate the controlled evaluation of cost-aware routing.

Efficiency metric (AGUC). To quantify the efficiency of adaptive supervision, we formulate *Accuracy Gain per Unit Cost (AGUC)*, which captures how efficiently supervision budget is converted into post-drift accuracy gains. It represents the improvement in post-drift accuracy over the static baseline divided by supervision cost during adaptation: $AGUC = (Acc_{\text{method}} - Acc_{\text{static}}) / TotalCost_{\text{method}}$.

5.2 Synthetic Stream: Controlled Drift Response

Figure 2 shows accuracy across time on the synthetic stream with an injected abrupt drift at $t = 500$. The static edge model suffers an immediate and lasting performance drop. In the absence of post-deployment supervision or adaptation, the model is unable to recover and continues to accumulate errors throughout the post-drift segment. This outcome serves as a lower-bound reference, and underscores the necessity of adaptive supervision mechanisms under abrupt drift.

SAL recovers gradually but with pronounced oscillations, reflecting repeated cycles of querying and retraining under elevated uncertainty. However, our approach recovers within approximately 40 samples and stabilizes shortly thereafter. The steep and monotonic recovery indicates efficient incorporation of corrective feedback without sustained external supervision.

Fig. 2: Accuracy and cumulative query counts on the synthetic stream with an injected abrupt drift at $t = 500$. The static model fails to recover, confirming sensitivity to shift. SAL restores performance but needs sustained querying after drift. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE obtains comparable accuracy with significantly lower supervision cost.

Table 1 shows that the Static Edge model avoids supervision cost but performs poorly after drift, while SAL improves accuracy at high human cost. In contrast, SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves faster recovery with lower cumulative cost, dominating all baselines in AGUC.

Method	#queries	Cost/query	Total cost	Mean acc.	AGUC
Static	0	0	0.00	0.6335	–
SAL	290	10	2900.00	0.8711	0.082
ADWIN-SAL	287	10	2870.00	0.9064	0.095
SYMBIOSIS-EDGE	297	0/1/10	1273.00	0.9351	0.237

Table 1: Cost summary on SYNTHETIC. Static has zero supervision cost. SAL and ADWIN-SAL are costed as human supervision. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE reserves human supervision for only the most uncertain cases.

5.3 SECOM Dataset: Real Industrial Sensor Drift

Figure 3 reports accuracy on the SECOM dataset under gradual industrial drift. The static edge model degrades steadily, indicating limited durability to developing conditions. SAL improves accuracy but adapts slowly, while SYMBIOSIS-EDGE maintains higher performance across most of the stream and converges faster to a stable regime, with fewer oscillations despite gradual drift.

Fig. 3: Accuracy and cumulative query counts on the SECOM semiconductor dataset under evolving operating conditions. In the absence of an explicit drift marker, static inference degrades progressively. SAL improves performance but incurs sustained query accumulation. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE maintains higher and more stable accuracy.

Table 2 exhibits the same trend under gradual drift. The static model shows low accuracy at zero cost, while SAL improves performance but at a high human cost. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves higher accuracy at roughly half the cost, resulting in substantially higher AGUC under progressive shifts.

Method	#queries	Cost/query	Total cost	Mean acc.	AGUC
Static	0	0	0.00	0.6281	–
SAL	300	10	3000.00	0.8678	0.080
ADWIN-SAL	298	10	2980.00	0.9059	0.093
SYMBIOSIS-EDGE	298	0/1/10	1291.00	0.9502	0.250

Table 2: Cost summary on SECOM. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves the highest accuracy while reducing total supervision cost by more than 50% compared to SAL-based baselines, yielding the best AGUC.

5.4 APS Dataset: Long-Horizon Degradation Patterns

Figure 4 shows accuracy on the APS dataset under long-horizon degradation. The static model underperforms persistently, while SAL improves accuracy but adapts slowly due to rare faults. In contrast, SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves higher accuracy across the stream, remaining effective under gradual drift.

Fig. 4: Accuracy and cumulative query counts on the APS dataset characterized by long-horizon degradation and rare fault events. Static inference underperforms persistently. SAL improves accuracy but requires steady supervisory input across the stream. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves smoother trajectories and lower cumulative supervision.

Table 3 confirms the pattern for long-horizon degradation with rare faults. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves the highest mean accuracy and AGUC.

Method	#queries	Cost/query	Total cost	Mean acc.	AGUC
Static	0	0	0.00	0.6351	–
SAL	306	10	3060.00	0.8512	0.071
ADWIN-SAL	296	10	2960.00	0.9011	0.090
SYMBIOSIS-EDGE	311	0/1/10	1354.00	0.9400	0.225

Table 3: Cost summary on APS. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE achieves the highest accuracy and AGUC while reducing supervision cost compared to SAL-based baselines.

5.5 Sensitivity Analysis

Cost ratios and supervision budgets are treated as normalized parameters rather than fixed assumptions, so the analysis depends on relative ordering rather than absolute prices. Sensitivity analysis shows consistent gains across plausible ranges, pointing to a structural effect rather than dependence on specific pricing. A 1:10 oracle-to-human cost ratio reflects realistic conditions, where expert supervision dominates costs. Assuming 60 EUR/hour for humans and 6 EUR/hour for the LLM (0.01 EUR/query, 600 queries/hour), edge inference is negligible. Under this model, SYMBIOSIS-EDGE outperforms continuous human supervision, achieving relative cost gains of 1:1.418 (synthetic), 1:1.577 (SECOM), and 1:1.755 (APS). These gains persist under non-linear cost functions, indicating a structural advantage of supervision routing over query-centric adaptation.

5.6 Ablation Study

We evaluate four ablated variants (Table 4) to isolate component contributions. The oracle and adaptive budget control account for most gains: the oracle handles intermediate-uncertainty samples at lower cost, while quantile thresholds prevent overload during drift. Both are necessary to reach the AGUC advantage. No variant achieves a better cost–accuracy trade-off; the proposed routing formulation dominates the evaluated baselines in cost–accuracy trade-offs.

Variant	SYNTHETIC			SECOM			APS		
	Acc	Cost	AGUC	Acc	Cost	AGUC	Acc	Cost	AGUC
SYMBIOSIS-EDGE	0.935	1273	0.237	0.950	1291	0.250	0.940	1354	0.225
No Oracle	0.904	2139	0.126	0.912	2221	0.128	0.911	2180	0.126
Fixed Thresholds	0.887	1795	0.141	0.925	1743	0.170	0.906	1869	0.145
Uniform Learning	0.921	1273	0.226	0.930	1291	0.234	0.924	1354	0.213

Table 4: Ablation study. Each row removes a component from the framework.

5.7 Computational Overhead

The routing mechanism introduces negligible overhead, as entropy is computed from existing model outputs in a single forward pass. Quantile thresholds are updated using sliding window statistics with $O(1)$ amortized cost.

5.8 Threats to Validity

The routing and budget-control mechanisms are independent of the specific oracle implementation. We validate them by replacing the oracle with a live LLM under real API conditions, obtaining matching recovery dynamics. This shows that the simulator captures the relevant cost–accuracy trade-offs while enabling controlled evaluation. The simulator is best understood as a parametric family of supervision sources rather than a proxy for any specific model. The use of entropy as a ranking signal is supported empirically by the performance gains.

The evaluation injects drift, whereas real deployments may involve rare events. Cost parameters and budgets are deployment parameters that should be calibrated with domain experts for industrial use. We also assume consistent human labeling quality; modeling annotator variability is left for future work.

Real LLM Instantiation. We validate that the routing mechanism transfers to a live LLM oracle. The simulated Oracle was replaced with ChatGPT 5.2 (via API, March 2026) using the same structured prompt templates as in the main experiments. The live-LLM validation reproduced the same method ordering, with accuracy deviations below 2% and similar escalation ratios across all datasets. Due to latency constraints, current LLMs are best treated as selective supervision channels rather than continuous online supervisors. The experiment confirms that routing and budget-control mechanisms transfer across oracle instantiations, and that the observed cost advantages are preserved under real API profiles. Figure 5 reports accuracy and cumulative query counts across all datasets. Results confirm comparable behavior, supporting the oracle-agnostic nature of the approach. Supplementary tests performed using Llama 3 and Mistral reiterate this comparable performance.

Fig. 5: Accuracy and cumulative query counts using ChatGPT-5.2 as the live Oracle across all datasets. Escalation patterns and recovery dynamics remain consistent with the simulated Oracle results.

6 Related Work

We combine streaming learning under drift, industrial Edge AI, cost-aware human supervision, and LLM-assisted analytics. Our review situates SYMBIOSIS-EDGE and explains the effect of coordinating the three models as decision sources.

6.1 Concept Drift in Data Streams

Concept drift concerns learning under changing data distributions [2]. Prior work categorizes drift types and temporal patterns, and relies on error monitoring or distribution tests for detection, with adaptive windowing as a standard online approach [3,10]. Ensemble methods are commonly used for adaptation in streaming settings [8], and libraries such as River support incremental evaluation [11]. Most approaches assume regular label availability or focus on drift detection itself. In industrial environments, however, expert supervision is scarce [5]. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE shifts the focus from detection to budget-driven uncertainty routing, where escalation decisions follow supervision costs.

6.2 Edge AI and Industrial Analytics

Edge AI enables low-latency, data-local inference near sensors. Prior work highlights constraints such as limited compute, memory, and hardware heterogeneity, as well as security and orchestration challenges across cloud–edge–fog systems [7,13]. In industrial settings, these architectures are driven by responsiveness and governance requirements [14], with communication efficiency remaining critical [16]. Systems such as AIFES address deployment and on-device learning under resource constraints [17]. These efforts motivate the engineering layer of SYMBIOSIS-EDGE, but largely ignore drift adaptation under costly supervision.

6.3 Human-in-the-Loop Learning and Budgeted Supervision

Active learning reduces labeling effort through selective querying, but settings require stable policies that avoid overloading annotators [9]. In Industry 5.0, humans remain responsible for decisions and audits, requiring interpretability and clear human–AI roles. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE treats humans as verifiers of structured hypotheses and bounds their involvement through explicit routing budgets. The routing problem is related to multi-armed bandit formulations with heterogeneous costs, but differs in that decisions are driven by uncertainty thresholds under explicit supervision budgets rather than reward maximization.

6.4 LLMs as Assistants at the Edge

Recent work studies LLM-based reasoning in data-intensive and edge systems. Architectures for autonomous edge intelligence and time series analysis highlight both opportunities and limitations [12,15]. LLMs are also discussed in data management and analytics pipelines [1,4,18]. Existing approaches typically use LLMs as advisory components. SYMBIOSIS-EDGE instead models the LLM as a cost-aware oracle with auditable and routable outputs.

6.5 Summary of Distinctions

To our knowledge, prior work does not combine these elements using a cost-aware routing formulation. Under drift, fixed query policies overload annotators, treat humans as label sources, and lack auditability. We route supervision across edge models, LLMs, and humans under cost constraints. Drift adaptation is treated as supervision routing across heterogeneous sources rather than retraining.

7 Conclusion

The paper’s central result is that drift adaptation is best treated as supervision routing under explicit budgets. Rather than treating adaptation as a retraining or query-triggering process, we model it as a decision problem over supervision resources. This separates model improvement from the routing of corrective supervision, enabling explicit control of cost, latency, and human effort. This formulation applies to industrial monitoring where expert attention is the primary bottleneck.

Our contribution is the formalization of uncertainty resolution as a budgeted routing decision. The routing policy routes samples across agents based on entropy and cost structure, independent of the specific implementation of intermediate supervision sources. This supports the rapid recovery from drift while preserving supervision resources. Experiments on several streams show that this coordination yields higher post-drift accuracy and return on supervision cost than standard approaches. A sensitivity analysis confirms that the cost advantages hold across a realistic pricing range.

Our architecture integrates on-device adaptation, oracle outputs, and quantile-based budget control into a real-time solution; the evaluation targets routing and budget behavior across supervision channels. The central decision is which agent should resolve each uncertain instance under fixed budgets, which makes supervision routing a measurable decision problem with economic consequences.

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